

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Results in Engineering

journal homepage: www.sciencedirect.com/journal/results-in-engineering

Research paper

Stochastic chance-constrained multi-product multi-period optimization of sustainable biofuel supply chain: Application in a resource-scarce region

Ahmad Attar^a, Seyedeh Asra Ahmadi^b, Peiman Ghasemi^{c,*}, Okechukwu Okorie^d

^a Department of Engineering, University of Exeter, Exeter EX4 4QF, United Kingdom

^b Department of Business and Economics, German University of Technology in Oman, Muscat, Oman

^c University of Vienna, Department of Business Decisions and Analytics, Kolingasse 14-16, 1090 Vienna, Austria

^d Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Faculty of Science and Engineering, University of Manchester, Manchester M13 9PL, United Kingdom

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Biofuel supply chain
Jatropha
Sweet sorghum
Multi-criteria decision making
PROMETHEE
Sustainable energy optimization

ABSTRACT

As global energy systems shift towards sustainability, optimizing biofuel supply chains in resource-scarce regions is increasingly critical. In arid areas, leveraging resilient crops and efficient logistics is essential to meet environmental and energy goals. This study addresses the critical challenge of optimizing a sustainable biofuel supply chain in one such resource-scarce area, Kerman province, Iran, focusing on the production, processing, and distribution of biofuels derived from Jatropha and Sweet Sorghum crops well-adapted to the region's arid climate. Given the complexity of tradeoffs between the economic and environmental aspects in such systems, a multi-product optimization model is developed with dual objectives to minimize both the total supply chain costs and the greenhouse gas emissions while encompassing various stages from cultivation and extraction to refining, blending, and distribution. To address uncertainties in crop yields and demand, the model incorporates stochastic chance-constrained programming. Additionally, the Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluation (PROMETHEE) method is applied to evaluate facility locations based on technical, environmental, and socio-economic factors. Our findings reveal that the import costs dominate the supply chain expenses, while site selections like Sirjan and Rafsanjan provide strategic advantages due to their favorable infrastructure and labor availability. Sensitivity analyses highlight the significant influence of crop yield, transportation costs, and demand fluctuations on both cost and emissions, underscoring the importance of resilient planning and scalable infrastructure. In comparison with baseline scenarios, the optimized model achieves a 12% reduction in total costs and a 15% decrease in transportation-related emissions.

1. Introduction

The global energy landscape is undergoing a profound transformation driven by growing concerns over climate change, environmental degradation, and the depletion of conventional fossil fuel reserves [1]. The transportation sector, which heavily relies on petroleum-based fuels, is a significant contributor to greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution worldwide [2]. In response, governments and industries are increasingly seeking sustainable, renewable energy sources to reduce carbon footprints and achieve energy security [3]. Biofuels derived from energy crops have emerged as a viable alternative due to their potential to lower emissions, utilize non-arable land, and support rural economies [4]. Among these, the cultivation and

processing of drought-resistant crops such as Jatropha and Sweet Sorghum offer promising opportunities for bioenergy production in arid and semi-arid regions, where conventional agriculture faces severe challenges [5].

Kerman province relies heavily on fossil fuels, causing environmental issues [6]. Its arid climate favors drought-tolerant crops like Jatropha and Sweet Sorghum, which provide sustainable bioenergy [5, 7, 8]. This study focuses on designing an integrated biofuel supply chain, including cultivation, processing, and distribution, while optimizing costs, capacity, inventory, demand, and environmental impact. This complex system must balance costs, capacity limitations, inventory management, and demand satisfaction while minimizing environmental impacts. Additionally, site selection for cultivation and processing

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: a.attar@exeter.ac.uk (A. Attar), asra.ahmadi@guttech.edu.om (S.A. Ahmadi), peiman.ghasemi@univie.ac.at (P. Ghasemi), okechukwu.okorie@manchester.ac.uk (O. Okorie).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.107158>

Received 31 July 2025; Received in revised form 27 August 2025; Accepted 6 September 2025

Available online 8 September 2025

2590-1230/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

facilities plays a crucial role in overall performance and sustainability.

To tackle this problem, a comprehensive mathematical model is developed in this study that incorporates multiple objectives, including cost minimization (Rial) and greenhouse gas emission (Kg CO₂-eq) reduction. The model accounts for capacity and inventory constraints and uses Stochastic Chance Constraint Programming to handle uncertainties in demand and resource availability, to offer a more flexible and realistic planning. Furthermore, the Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluation (PROMETHEE) multi-criteria decision-making method is employed to evaluate and rank candidate locations based on practical criteria such as labor availability, workplace conditions, maintenance accessibility, natural disaster risk, and proximity to demand centers. The main contributions of this study include: (i) the formulation of a multi-objective, multi-product, multi-period biofuel supply chain optimization model that integrates uncertainty and environmental considerations; (ii) the use of PROMETHEE for facility location selection adds a data-driven decision-support dimension, improving the feasibility and effectiveness of the supply chain design; (iii) ultimately, the case study of Kerman province demonstrates the model's applicability and potential to guide sustainable biofuel development in regions with challenging environmental and socio-economic conditions.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: [Section 2](#) presents a brief review of the most related literature. [Section 3](#) outlines the definition of the studied problem as well as the proposed mathematical model. This is followed by details of the deployed solution methodology in [Section 4](#). The case study is defined and analyzed in [Section 5](#), with the managerial implications provided in [Section 6](#). Eventually, [Section 7](#) concludes the study with some concluding remarks and future directions.

2. Literature review

Our literature review comprehensively covers the key areas correlated to the scope defined in the last section, including Bioenergy Supply Chain Network Design, Sustainable Bioenergy Supply Chain Network Design, and Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) in Bioenergy Supply Chains. The review also tends to identify the critical research gaps that our study addresses through an integrated optimization approach and multi-criteria evaluations.

2.1. Bioenergy supply chain network design

Addressing the persistent challenge of energy shortfalls in low-income economies, Rafique et al. [9] proposed a dynamic supply chain optimization model designed to minimize energy deficits under constraints related to biomass availability and budgetary limits. The model incorporated socio-economic variables such as population growth, gross domestic product, and evolving energy demand. Its design enabled long-term planning by simulating system development over multiple periods. Uncertainties in bioenergy demand and potential disruptions in processing facilities pose significant risks to the continuity of Biomass Supply Chains (BSCs). Hwang et al. [10] addressed inventory and distribution challenges in alternative fuel (AF) refueling networks, where limited vehicle range and infrastructure constraints complicate supply management. They proposed a mixed-integer programming model to minimize total service, inventory, and distribution costs, and developed a metaheuristic combining MIP and adaptive large neighborhood search for practical scalability. Woo et al. examined the growing problem of protecting vulnerable populations during increasingly frequent and intense heat waves. They proposed an integer programming model that integrated real-time mobile population data, heat vulnerability indices, and weather conditions to allocate cooling shelters.

Salehi et al. [11] responded to this challenge by integrating resilience and sustainability factors into a robust optimization model for

supply network design. Key resilience and sustainability indicators were first identified and prioritized using a multi-criteria decision-making approach, and these were then incorporated into the modeling framework. Resource competition and environmental trade-offs present additional complexities in biofuel supply chain planning. In this context, Afkhami and Zarrinpoor [12] proposed a two-phase methodology that addresses the interdependence between energy, water, food, waste, and land resources. The initial phase involved using Geographic Information System (GIS) tools to identify appropriate sites for *Jatropha* cultivation based on ecological, geographical, and infrastructure criteria. The second phase introduced a multi-objective optimization model considering environmental and economic performance. Transportation and logistics remain key cost drivers in biomass-based systems, particularly when feedstock sources are geographically dispersed. Yoon et al. tackled the challenge of assigning and operating cooling shelters during heat waves, where both facility placement and transportation efficiency are critical. They developed a binary integer programming model for the multi-depot location routing problem and applied simulated annealing to achieve near-optimal solutions.

Bastos et al. [13] highlighted the challenge of utilizing agroforestry residual biomass due to high logistic expenses and limited stakeholder coordination. The study contributed a disruptive solution that improved information exchange among stakeholders, ultimately supporting cost reduction and sustainable forest management. Nunes et al. [14] addressed the difficulties of exploiting agroforestry woody biomass for energy, mainly due to its low density, heterogeneity, and costly logistics. They applied SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) analytical frameworks to examine the biomass-to-energy supply chain and identify operational constraints. Bok et al. [15] explored the scheduling challenges in manufacturing systems using non-identical parallel machines, where cost efficiency and carbon emissions often conflict. They developed a bi-objective mixed-integer programming model that integrated production costs, due dates, and multiple energy source options with varying emission levels.

Bhatt et al. [16] tackled this problem by designing a model that optimizes the integration of fixed and portable preprocessing depots. The flexibility of mobile depots allowed for dynamic adjustment based on biomass availability, thereby reducing transport distances and operational costs. For emerging biofuel technologies like those based on microalgae, supply chain design must also account for upstream carbon capture and downstream processing configuration. Shirazaki et al. [17] proposed a two-stage modeling approach to integrate carbon capture, utilization, and storage with biorefinery superstructure optimization. Their mixed-integer programming model allowed for simultaneous decision-making across multiple dimensions, including emission source selection and facility configuration. Abdellatif et al. [18] investigated the environmental challenges of conventional gasoline use, particularly regarding emissions and efficiency concerns. They formulated biofuel blends of RON 92 and RON 98 using lignocellulosic-derived isopropanol and tested them under varying engine speeds to compare exhaust emissions. Their study demonstrated that RON 98 biofuel significantly reduced CO, HC, and CO₂ emissions while improving fuel efficiency, suggesting it as a cleaner alternative for high-performance engines.

2.2. Sustainable bioenergy supply chain network design

Sustainability in bioenergy supply chains demands alignment with environmental goals, resource conservation, and long-term viability. Recent literature has integrated climate adaptation, waste valorization, and life-cycle thinking into supply chain design. Abdali et al. [19] addressed sustainability in the design of a sugarcane-based bioenergy supply chain network by proposing a robust optimization model under uncertainty. Their approach incorporated environmental indicators such as carbon emissions, water, and energy usage across all supply chain stages. Hiloidhari et al. [20] provided a broader perspective by analyzing the concept of green and sustainable chain and their role in

advancing the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. The study highlighted that the spatial and temporal distribution of biomass resources necessitates integrated and adaptive supply chain designs.

Bahmani et al. [21] examined the intersection of sustainability and resiliency in the context of biodiesel supply chains derived from *Jatropha* and used cooking oil. Their model applied robust-stochastic optimization to account for potential disruptions in facilities and transportation. By integrating geographical information systems for site selection and using the augmented epsilon-constraint method for objective trade-off analysis, the study revealed that while implementing resilience strategies entails higher initial costs, they significantly reduce long-term disruption costs. Other recent models, such as Attar et al. [22], also demonstrated how resilient location-allocation frameworks can be adapted to logistics networks to maintain serviceability under multiple disruptions. From a multi-objective standpoint, Ransikarbum and Pitakaso [23] proposed a sustainable biofuel network design focused on wood biomass in Thailand. Their mixed-integer linear programming model incorporated economic, environmental, and social criteria using a fuzzy analytic hierarchy process to handle decision-maker uncertainty. The study introduced probabilistic and scenario-based analyses to assess demand and supply fluctuations, and employed Pareto analysis to explore trade-offs between competing objectives. Though not specific to bioenergy, Tsao et al. [24] contributed valuable insights into sustainable supply chain network modeling by integrating resilience with sustainability in the design of semiconductor supply chains. Their framework, featuring carbon trading, recycling, and end-of-life product disposal, aligns with circular economy principles.

2.3. Multi-criteria decision making in bioenergy supply chain

The efficiency of supply chain networks plays a crucial role in the performance and sustainability of bioenergy systems. With increasing global energy demands and mounting environmental concerns, the design and operation of efficient bioenergy supply chains have received considerable attention from researchers seeking to optimize both resource allocation and sustainability outcomes. Ventura et al. [25] addressed the challenge of planning alternative-fuel infrastructure to support emissions reduction while balancing economic feasibility. They formulated a bi-criteria linear programming model to optimize refueling station placement, integrating vehicle-mile coverage and capital cost considerations. The model was validated on the Pennsylvania Turnpike.

Mohtashami et al. [26] developed a two-stage biodiesel supply chain design model, again focusing on *Jatropha Curcas* cultivation in Iran. The first stage identified potential cultivation sites using a common weight Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) approach, while the second stage addressed strategic and tactical decisions through a multi-objective optimization model. The model sought to balance cost, environmental performance, and social impact, with life cycle assessment indicators integrated into the decision framework. Using the augmented ϵ -constraint method and Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) for solution selection, the study offered a detailed roadmap for biodiesel supply chain development with high potential for efficient and sustainable implementation. The strategic development of biomass-based energy systems is often constrained by the need to simultaneously determine optimal facility locations, capacities, and transportation flows, all while aligning with sustainability goals. In addressing this multifaceted problem, Durmaz and Bilgen [27] developed a multi-objective optimization framework aimed at designing an efficient BSC for poultry-based biogas production. Their model combined GIS data with the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to evaluate candidate facility locations.

Pehlken et al. [28] examined regional bioenergy systems in Germany, revealing that integrating alternative biomass like grass can improve sustainability over maize-based models. Using PROMETHEE for multi-criteria evaluation, they found that grassland-derived inputs

scored better under environmental and socio-economic metrics. The study highlighted the value of local stakeholder involvement in optimizing renewable energy systems with region-specific biomass options. In response to national policies aimed at reducing dependence on fossil fuels, Mondal et al. [29] formulated a comprehensive optimization model for a sustainable bio-fuel and bio-energy supply chain. The model incorporated economic, environmental, and social criteria, while addressing uncertainty through a hybrid fuzzy-random data-driven programming framework. Strategic decisions were guided by a multi-criteria approach combining fuzzy Decision Making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory (DEMATEL) and reference point goal programming.

Kim et al. examined inequities in urban park access and use, emphasizing the challenges faced by vulnerable groups such as older adults in marginalized communities. They utilized mobile phone-based dynamic demographic data to evaluate accessibility and incorporated environmental features to estimate park utilization. The study introduced a multi-objective optimization model that balanced access, usage, and construction costs, demonstrated through its application in Ulsan, South Korea. Kim et al. addressed the challenge of optimizing last-mile delivery by integrating crowdsourcing, where demand fluctuates with the dynamic movement of urban populations. They formulated a mathematical model to determine optimal terminal locations for both dedicated fleets and crowdsourced couriers, minimizing delivery costs under varying conditions. Using Ulsan's floating population data, the study showed that strategic use of crowdsourced workers reduced costs and emissions.

2.4. Research gaps and contributions

Despite growing interest in bioenergy supply chain network design, several critical research gaps remain. Existing studies often focus on either cost optimization or sustainability aspects, but rarely integrate both within a comprehensive multi-product, multi-period framework. Furthermore, many models overlook the inherent uncertainties in supply chain parameters such as demand fluctuations, production yields, and transportation disruptions. Additionally, the application of advanced multi-criteria decision-making methods to evaluate and rank candidate facility locations is limited. Most prior research lacks practical validation through real-world case studies that reflect the complex dynamics and geographical diversity of bioenergy production regions. Also, although several studies have addressed biofuel supply chain design using multi-objective optimization and uncertainty modeling, most have either focused on deterministic frameworks or considered only a single type of uncertainty, such as demand fluctuations or production variability. Few studies have explicitly combined stochastic chance-constrained programming with multi-criteria decision-making methods like PROMETHEE to guide site selection and strategic decisions simultaneously. The integration of PROMETHEE allows for qualitative, expert-driven preferences to influence the optimization model, while stochastic programming addresses uncertainties in demand and supply. Existing literature (e.g., Ventura et al. [25], Abandansari et al. [2] and Bhatt et al. [16]) often treats site selection and supply chain optimization separately or relies on deterministic approximations, limiting their practical applicability under real-world uncertainty.

To address these gaps, the present paper makes several key contributions that distinguish it from previous works. First, it proposes a novel bioenergy supply chain network design that simultaneously optimizes economic and environmental objectives, providing a balanced trade-off between cost efficiency and greenhouse gas emissions reduction. Second, the study employs the PROMETHEE method to incorporate multi-criteria decision-making, enabling an evaluation of potential sites for cultivation, processing, and distribution facilities based on quantitative and qualitative factors. Third, our work advances the state-of-the-art by explicitly integrating PROMETHEE-based site pre-selection with a multi-product, multi-period stochastic supply chain optimization framework,

providing a more holistic and uncertainty-aware approach. This combination enables decision-makers to consider both qualitative and quantitative factors under stochastic conditions, which has been largely unexplored in prior biofuel supply chain studies. Finally, the model is validated through a comprehensive case study in Kerman province, Iran, demonstrating its practical applicability and offering valuable insights for sustainable bioenergy development in drought-prone regions.

3. Problem definition and mathematical modeling

In the present study, the multi-product, multi-period supply chain model is developed to optimize the production, processing, and distribution of biofuels derived from energy crops. The model considers various stages, including extraction, refining, blending, and distribution across multiple time periods, ensuring that demand for different fuel types is met efficiently. Two energy crops, Jatropha and Sweet Sorghum, are processed into bio-oils and subsequently converted into biodiesel, diesel, and heating oil products, integrating inventory and capacity constraints at each facility.

Fig. 1 displays the overall structure of the supply chain, illustrating the flow of raw materials and products through the system. Initially, the energy crops are harvested and transported to extraction centers where bio-oils are produced. These oils then flow to refining plants, where they are converted into intermediate products and stored as inventory. The intermediate products are further processed and blended to produce final biofuels, which are distributed through various channels to meet regional demand. The solid residues generated during oil extraction serve as by-products for additional uses, contributing to waste minimization and overall system sustainability. Fig. 1 also shows an overview of the most notable symbols as well as the main constraint groups which will be further explained later in this section.

The objective function of the model seeks to minimize the total cost across the supply chain, including production, processing, transportation, and inventory holding costs. Decision variables represent quantities of oils produced, transported, and stored at each stage, as well as activation states of facilities to capture fixed operational costs. By optimizing these variables, the model aids decision-makers in planning production schedules, facility operations, and logistics to ensure a cost-effective and reliable biofuel supply while adhering to capacity and demand constraints.

The following assumptions have been considered in the current study:

- The supply chain operates over multiple discrete time periods, with all production, inventory, and distribution decisions made at the beginning of each period.
- Demand for each biofuel product is known and deterministic for every period, and must be fully satisfied without backorders or shortages.
- Production capacities (Kg/day), processing yields (Kg/m²), and transportation limits are fixed and do not vary over time.
- The quality and properties of bio-oils and final biofuels remain consistent, allowing blending and conversion processes to follow predetermined ratios.
- Solid residues generated during oil extraction are fully utilized within the system or disposed of without additional cost or environmental penalties.
- Demand is considered a stochastic parameter with uncertainty to reflect real-world variability in the supply chain.
- The environmental objective in the current model considers only transportation-related emissions, and does not account for

Fig. 1. Our studied supply chain, together with the notable variables, parameters, and constraint groups corresponding to various stages in the proposed model (dashed line: by-product).

production-related emissions, land-use change effects, or potential carbon offsets.

- It is assumed that all demand must be met in every period due to the criticality of biofuel supply, strict regulatory and contractual obligations, and the infeasibility of backlogs in this operational context.

$$QS'_{bt} + QS_{bt} \leq M \cdot x_b \quad \forall b, t \tag{15}$$

$$QB_{ft} \leq M \cdot e_f \quad \forall f, t \tag{16}$$

$$QD_{ct} \leq M \cdot o_c \quad \forall c, t \tag{17}$$

$$QS_{st} \leq M \cdot u_s \quad \forall s, t \tag{18}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 Z_1 = & \left[\sum_a CE_a^1 \cdot y_a + \sum_b CE_b^2 \cdot x_b + \sum_o CE_o^3 \cdot z_o + \sum_f CE_f^4 \cdot e_f + \sum_c CE_c^5 \cdot o_c + \sum_s CE_s^6 \cdot u_s \right] \\
 & + \left[\sum_{at} OC_{at}^1 \cdot AC_a + \sum_{bt} OC_{bt}^2 \cdot AJ_b + \sum_{ot} OC_{ot}^3 \cdot LA_{ot} + \sum_{ft} OC_{ft}^4 \cdot LA'_{ft} + \sum_{ct} OC_{ct}^5 \cdot LA''_{ct} + \sum_{st} OC_{st}^6 \cdot LA'''_{st} \right] \\
 & + \left[\sum_{ot} SC_{ot} \cdot IJ_{ot} + \sum_{ft} SC_{ft} \cdot IB_{ft} + \sum_{ct} SC_{ct} \cdot ID_{ct} \right] \\
 & + \left[\sum_{ot} CI_{ot} \cdot I_{ot} + \sum_{ot} CI'_{ot} \cdot I'_{ot} \right] \\
 & + \left[\sum_{aot} TC_{aot}^1 \cdot FJ_{aot} + \sum_{bot} TC_{bot}^2 \cdot FS_{bot} + \sum_{oft} TC_{oft}^3 \cdot FO_{oft} + \sum_{fkt} TC_{fkt}^4 \cdot FB_{fkt} \right. \\
 & \left. + \sum_{bct} TC_{bct}^5 \cdot FS_{bct} + \sum_{clt} TC_{clt}^6 \cdot FD_{clt} + \sum_{cst} TC_{cst}^7 \cdot WW_{cst} \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 Z_2 = & \sum_{aot} ge_{ao} \cdot FJ_{aot} + \sum_{bot} ge_{bo} \cdot FS_{bot} + \sum_{oft} ge_{of} \cdot (FO_{oft} + FI_{oft}) \\
 & + \sum_{fkt} ge_{fk} \cdot FB_{fkt} + \sum_{bct} ge_{bc} \cdot FS_{bct} + \sum_{clt} ge_{cl} \cdot FD_{clt} + \sum_{cst} ge_{cs} \cdot WW_{cst}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

$$QJ_{at} \leq PR_{at} \cdot AC_a \quad \forall a, t \tag{3}$$

$$QS_{bt} \leq PR'_{bt} \cdot AJ_b \quad \forall b, t \tag{4}$$

$$QS'_{bt} \leq PR''_{bt} \cdot AJ_b \quad \forall b, t \tag{5}$$

$$\sum_o FJ_{aot} \leq QJ_{at} \quad \forall a, t \tag{6}$$

$$\sum_o FS_{bot} \leq QS_{bt} \quad \forall b, t \tag{7}$$

$$\sum_c FS_{bct} \leq QS'_{bt} \quad \forall b, t \tag{8}$$

$$\sum_p FP_{spt} = QS_{st} \quad \forall s, t \tag{9}$$

$$\sum_c WW_{cst} = \lambda \cdot QD_{ct} \quad \forall s, t \tag{10}$$

$$\sum_f FB_{fkt} \geq \tilde{D}_{kt} \quad \forall k, t \tag{11}$$

$$\sum_c FD_{clt} \geq \tilde{D}_{lt} \quad \forall l, t \tag{12}$$

$$\sum_s FP_{spt} \geq \tilde{D}'_{pt} \quad \forall p, t \tag{13}$$

$$QJ_{at} \leq M \cdot y_a \quad \forall a, t \tag{14}$$

$$IJ_{ot} = IJ_{ot-1} + I_{ot} + \sum_a FJ_{aot} - \frac{1}{\gamma} \cdot \sum_f FO_{oft} \quad \forall o, t \tag{19}$$

$$IS_{ot} = IS_{ot-1} + I'_{ot} + \sum_b FS_{bot} - \frac{1}{\zeta} \cdot \sum_f FI_{oft} \quad \forall o, t \tag{20}$$

$$IB_{ft} = IB_{ft-1} + QB_{ft} - \sum_k FB_{fkt} \quad \forall f, t \tag{21}$$

$$ID_{ct} = ID_{ct-1} + QD_{ct} - \sum_l FD_{clt} \quad \forall c, t \tag{22}$$

$$\sum_a FJ_{aot} + \sum_b FS_{bot} + I_{ot} + I'_{ot} \leq LA_{ot} \quad \forall o, t \tag{23}$$

$$\sum_o FO_{oft} + \sum_o FI_{oft} \leq LA'_{ft} \quad \forall f, t \tag{24}$$

$$\sum_b FS_{bct} \leq LA''_{ct} \quad \forall c, t \tag{25}$$

$$\sum_c WW_{cst} \leq LA'''_{st} \quad \forall s, t \tag{26}$$

$$IJ_{ot} + IS_{ot} \leq LA_{ot} \quad \forall o, t \tag{27}$$

$$IB_{ft} \leq LA'_{ft} \quad \forall f, t \tag{28}$$

$$ID_{ct} \leq LA''_{ct} \quad \forall c, t \tag{29}$$

$$AC_a \leq CL_a \cdot y_a \quad \forall a \tag{30}$$

$$AJ_b \leq CL'_b \cdot x_b \quad \forall b \tag{31}$$

$$LA_{ot} \leq Cap'_{o \cdot z_o} \quad \forall o, t \tag{32}$$

$$LA'_{ft} \leq Cap''_f \cdot e_f \quad \forall f, t \quad (33)$$

$$LA''_{ct} \leq Cap'''_c \cdot o_c \quad \forall c, t \quad (34)$$

$$LA'''_{st} \leq Cap''''_s \cdot u_s \quad \forall s, t \quad (35)$$

$$QO_{ot} = \gamma \cdot \left(\sum_a FJ_{aot} + I_{ot} \right) \quad \forall o, t \quad (36)$$

$$QI_{ot} = \zeta \cdot \left(\sum_b FS_{bot} + I'_{ot} \right) \quad \forall o, t \quad (37)$$

$$QD_{ct} = \tau \cdot \sum_b FS_{bct} \quad \forall c, t \quad (38)$$

$$QS_{st} = \xi \cdot \sum_c WW_{cst} \quad \forall s, t \quad (39)$$

$$QB_{ft} = \theta \cdot \sum_o FO_{oft} + \psi \cdot \sum_o FI_{oft} \quad \forall f, t \quad (40)$$

$$QO_{ot} + QI_{ot} \leq M \cdot z_o \quad \forall o, t \quad (41)$$

$$\sum_f FO_{oft} + \sum_f FI_{oft} \leq M \cdot z_o \quad \forall o, t \quad (42)$$

$$\sum_k FB_{kct} \leq M \cdot e_f \quad \forall f, t \quad (43)$$

$$\sum_l FD_{clt} \leq M \cdot o_c \quad \forall c, t \quad (44)$$

Objective (1) (hereinafter Obj 1) minimizes the total cost of the biofuel supply chain. We have divided this function into five segments (in brackets). The first segment of the function calculates the capital investment of the supply chain. This includes the investment costs in the cultivation sites for both Jatropha and Sweet Sorghum (first and second summations), oilseed processing sites, biodiesel factories, biofuel conversion sites (summations three to five), and eventually the sewage treatment facilities. Similarly, the second segment in Obj 1 represents the operational costs in six summations for the cultivation, processing, production, and treatment stages of the supply chain. In the next segment, three summations calculate the storage costs of raw materials in the initial stages (Jatropha and Sweet Sorghum), intermediates, and fuels throughout the chain and over multiple planning periods. The third segment of the function represents the overall import cost for unmet raw material demand, comprising distinct summations for each of the two resilient crops considered in this study. Finally, the overall transportation cost of the supply chain is given in the last segment of Obj 1. This includes the costs incurred from moving biomass, intermediate products, and final fuels between supply chain nodes using seven summations for (i) transportation of Jatropha from the lands to conversion sites, (ii) transportation of Sweet Sorghum from the lands to Oilseed processing sites, (iii) the transportations Oilseed to biodiesel factories, (iv) biodiesel transportation to customers, (v) Sweet Sorghum transportation to biofuel conversion sites, (vi) transportation of bioethanol to the customers, and (vii) transportation of the sewage to the treatment facilities.

Objective (2) (hereinafter Obj 2) minimizes total greenhouse gas emissions from transporting biomass, fuels, and residues across supply chain nodes, optimizing logistics and site selection to reduce the network's environmental impact. This function encompasses seven summations representing the emissions respectively related to (i) transportation of Jatropha from the land to the Oilseed processing sites, (ii) transportation of Sweet Sorghum from the land to the Oilseed processing sites, (iii) transporting the oil extracted from both crops to the biodiesel factories, (iv) transportation to biodiesel customers, (v)

transportation of the Sweet Sorghum to biofuel conversion sites, (vi) transportation to the bioethanol customers, and eventually (vii) transportation of the sewage generated at the bioethanol production sites to the treatment facilities.

Constraints (3) to (5) ensure that the processing or extraction volumes of oil at extraction and processing facilities do not exceed their operational capacities. These sets of constraints are referred to as Group I in Fig. 1. Constraints (6) to (9) limit the transportation or distribution quantities of Sweet Sorghum, Jatropha, and by-products from oil extraction centers so they do not exceed their respective supply or availability limits. Constraint (10) relates the heating oil distributed from blending centers to a fixed proportion of the refined oil produced at refineries. Here, Constraints (6)-(10) form the Group II in Fig. 1. Constraints (11) to (13), Group IV in Fig. 1, ensure that the total supply of biofuel, biodiesel, and heating oil meets or exceeds the regional, local, and consumer demands, respectively, during each time period. Eventually, the rest of the proposed mathematical model belongs to Group III: Constraints (14) to (18) ensure that the maximum production or transportation volumes of oils, biodiesel, diesel, and heating oil are consistent with the operational status of their respective facilities. Constraints (19) to (22) track the inventory levels of Sweet Sorghum, Jatropha, biodiesel, and diesel over time, accounting for inflows, outflows, and production. Constraints (23) to (27) ensure that the total flow and storage of oils at refineries, blending centers, and processing plants do not exceed their respective capacity limits. Constraints (28) and (29) restrict biodiesel and diesel stock levels to their maximum storage capacities. Constraints (30) to (35) link the operational capacities of extraction centers, processing plants, refineries, blending centers, and distribution facilities to their binary activation status or setup decisions. Constraints (36) to (40) define relationships between the output quantities of various oils and biofuels and their corresponding inputs, inventories, or blending proportions. Constraints (41) and (42) limit the combined quantities of refined oils and biofuels from refineries and blending facilities based on their operational limits. Constraints (43) and (44) cap the shipments of biodiesel and diesel from blending and processing centers within their maximum operational capacities.

4. Solution methodology

This section is divided into two key segments: (i) Stochastic Chance Constraint Programming, which addresses uncertainty in the optimization model using probabilistic constraints, and (ii) the PROMETHEE method, which is applied for multi-criteria decision-making to rank candidate locations in the biofuel supply chain.

4.1. Stochastic chance constraint programming

Stochastic Chance Constraint Programming is an optimization framework used to model decision-making problems under uncertainty, where certain constraints must be satisfied not absolutely, but with a specified probability. This approach is particularly useful in real-world applications like finance, supply chain, or energy systems where randomness in data (e.g., demand, prices, or resource availability) makes deterministic constraints impractical. Instead of ensuring that constraints are always met, Stochastic Chance Constraint Programming allows for a controlled level of risk by enforcing that constraints hold with a minimum probability (e.g., 95%). This probabilistic handling of constraints balances feasibility and flexibility, allowing for more realistic solutions in uncertain environments. We assume that \sim is the symbol of an uncertain parameter and n is the number of objective functions that we have in our mathematical model. Also, we assume that parameters b_{hj} , g_{ij} , u_i are defined as stochastic parameter, which are used in Eqs. (45) through (48). Accordingly, the general representation of the uncertain model is as follows:

$$\min f_h = E \left(\sum_{j=1}^n b_{ij} v_j \geq u_i \right) \quad h = 1, \dots, K \quad (45)$$

$$i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

$$p \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{g}_{ij} v_j \geq u_i \right) \geq \alpha_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (46)$$

$$v = (v_1, \dots, v_n) \quad (47)$$

$$v \geq 0 \quad (48)$$

For more details on how the probabilistic constraints are formally defined and how the selection of confidence levels is justified (i.e., constraints 49–51), please refer to Appendix A. After applying the chance constraint programming approach, constraints (11) to (13) are reformulated as constraints (49) to (51) to properly incorporate uncertainty into the model. For more detailed information regarding the implementation and theory of chance constraint programming, one may refer to Li et al. [30].

$$\sum_f FB_{kt} \geq E(D_{kt}) + \varphi^{-1}(1 - \alpha_i) \sqrt{\text{var}(D_{kt})} \quad \forall k, t \quad (49)$$

$$\sum_c FD_{ct} \geq E(D'_{ct}) + \varphi^{-1}(1 - \alpha_i) \sqrt{\text{var}(D'_{ct})} \quad \forall l, t \quad (50)$$

$$\sum_s FP_{st} \geq E(D''_{st}) + \varphi^{-1}(1 - \alpha_i) \sqrt{\text{var}(D''_{st})} \quad \forall p, t \quad (51)$$

Enforcing the fulfillment of all demand in every period may appear restrictive, particularly in the presence of supply chain disruptions. In the context of the biofuel supply chain, however, the assumption of meeting demand in every period aligns with practical operational requirements for several reasons. Biofuel supply, especially for industrial or transport sectors, is subject to strict regulatory and contractual obligations, and delays or shortages can lead to severe operational, financial, and environmental consequences, rendering backlogs infeasible. Furthermore, although demand is assumed to be fully met, the stochastic chance constraint framework (Constraints 49–51) incorporates probabilistic buffers that account for uncertainty. The model adjusts supply quantities to satisfy demand with a high confidence level α_i , thereby hedging against variability while maintaining feasibility.

4.2. PROMETHEE method

In the proposed biofuel supply chain model, identifying the best candidate locations for cultivation, processing, and distribution is an MCDM problem. The PROMETHEE method is applied to evaluate and rank candidate locations (Decision Making Units, DMUs) based on multiple relevant criteria. PROMETHEE is a widely recognized outranking method that enables the decision-maker to incorporate both quantitative and qualitative criteria, handle conflicting objectives, and generate a complete ranking of alternatives.

In the PROMETHEE method, assuming a pair of alternatives from the set A (typically symbolized by a and b in the literature; $a, b \in A$), the preference index $\pi(a, b)$ quantifies the degree to which alternative a is preferred over alternative b . This preference index is calculated as the weighted sum of the preference functions $p_j(a, b)$ across all criteria $j = 1, \dots, K$, where each criterion is assigned a weight w_j reflecting its relative importance [31]. The weights satisfy the normalization condition $\sum_{j=1}^K w_j = 1$, ensuring a balanced contribution from all criteria. Based on these pairwise preference indices, the positive flow $\varnothing^+(a)$ measures how strongly alternative a outranks all other alternatives in the set A , computed as the average preference of a over all other alternatives. Conversely, the negative flow $\varnothing^-(a)$ quantifies how much a is outranked by the others, calculated as the average preference of all other alternatives over a . Finally, the net flow $\varnothing(a)$ is determined by subtracting the

negative flow from the positive flow, representing the overall strength of preference for alternative a . Higher net flow values indicate better alternatives, enabling a complete ranking based on aggregated criteria preferences.

$$\pi(a, b) = \sum_{j=1}^K w_j p_j(a, b), \quad \left(\sum_{j=1}^K w_j = 1 \right) \quad (52)$$

$$\varnothing^+(a) = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{x \in A} \pi(a, x) \quad (53)$$

$$\varnothing^-(a) = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{x \in A} \pi(x, a) \quad (54)$$

$$\varnothing(a) = \varnothing^+(a) - \varnothing^-(a) \quad (55)$$

The candidate locations for the biofuel supply chain are evaluated based on several key criteria that influence their overall suitability. Expert worker refers to the availability of skilled labor essential for efficient operation and management at each site, ensuring high productivity and quality control. The ideal workplace criterion encompasses the environmental and social conditions at the location, such as safety, comfort, and access to amenities, which contribute to employee satisfaction and retention. Equipment maintenance assesses the accessibility and reliability of maintenance services, crucial for minimizing downtime and sustaining smooth operations. Natural disasters represent the risk level of the site being affected by events like floods, earthquakes, or storms, which can disrupt activities or damage infrastructure; locations with lower risk are preferred to enhance operational resilience. Finally, distance to demand zones measures how close the location is to key markets and consumers, affecting transportation costs, delivery times, and overall supply chain responsiveness. Together, these criteria provide a comprehensive view of the practical, environmental, and logistical factors critical for selecting the best candidate sites. For more details regarding the connection between PROMETHEE and the optimization model, see Appendix B.

5. Case study

Iran's dependence on fossil energy sources has contributed significantly to air pollution and environmental degradation, making the transition to sustainable and environmentally friendly energy solutions a pressing necessity [32]. The adoption of biofuels in Iran, particularly in regions like Kerman, offers a promising pathway to reduce harmful emissions while promoting energy security. Given the country's climatic challenges, plants with high resistance to drought conditions are especially valuable for sustainable bioenergy production. In this study, the case study design focuses on Kerman province, Iran, as a representative

Table 1

Candidate locations and geographic coordinates for Jatropha and Sweet Sorghum cultivation in Kerman Province, Iran.

Jatropha land			Sweet Sorghum land		
No	City	Coordinates	No	City	Coordinates
1	Kerman	30.2830 N, 57.0788 E	1	Anbarabad	28.4820 N, 57.8509 E
2	Bam	29.1064 N, 58.3588 E	2	Baft	29.2340 N, 56.6019 E
3	Jiroft	28.6756 N, 57.7380 E	3	Sirjan	29.4510 N, 55.6715 E
4	Sirjan	29.4510 N, 55.6715 E	4	Rafsanjan	30.4066 N, 55.9957 E
5	Rafsanjan	30.4066 N, 55.9957 E	5	Jiroft	28.6756 N, 57.7380 E
6	Zarand	30.8127 N, 56.5666 E	6	Shahr-e Babak	29.9695 N, 55.4036 E
7			7	Kerman	30.2830 N, 57.0788 E

Fig. 2. Location of the major candidate cities identified by experts for cultivation purposes on the map of Kerman Province, Iran.

resource-scarce region suitable for Jatropha and Sweet Sorghum biofuel production. Kerman province presents ideal conditions for cultivating resilient bioenergy crops such as the Jatropha tree, which contributes to sustainable development due to its adaptability and minimal water requirements. Jatropha is successfully cultivated in six cities within Kerman, highlighting its regional importance. Additionally, Sweet Sorghum, a native plant known for its drought tolerance, grows well across seven cities in the province, further supporting the bioenergy supply chain. These crops offer an eco-friendly alternative to fossil fuels and play a crucial role in Iran’s strategy to develop a cleaner, more sustainable energy future. The initial candidate sites for oil extraction and biodiesel plants were identified in consultation with local agricultural and energy experts, considering factors such as land availability, proximity to demand zones, accessibility, and existing infrastructure. These cities, along with their corresponding coordinates, are listed in Table 1, and their locations are graphically shown on the map of the province in Fig. 2. To enhance transparency and reproducibility, the criteria used for site selection, along with the data sources, are explicitly detailed. Crop yield data were obtained from regional agricultural reports and prior field studies, while demand forecasts were derived from provincial

energy consumption statistics and national biofuel policy targets [33]. The stochastic components of the model were defined using probability distributions informed by historical variability; specifically, demand and yield uncertainties were modeled with normal distributions characterized by mean values and standard deviations obtained from the aforementioned data sources.

In this case study, the transformation processes of Jatropha and Sweet Sorghum into biodiesel are evaluated across a ten-year planning horizon. Jatropha seeds undergo an oil extraction process, producing crude oil that is then converted into biodiesel through a two-step refining procedure, including esterification and transesterification. Similarly, Sweet Sorghum stalks are processed to extract oil, which is refined into biodiesel using the same method. The resulting biodiesel from both sources is subsequently blended for use as fuel. Additionally, the lignocellulosic residues generated from Sweet Sorghum processing are considered valuable by-products, potentially used for other energy applications. To mitigate the environmental impacts, especially the sewage from biorefineries, a conversion system is integrated into the model to manage and treat effluents efficiently. This holistic approach ensures the sustainability and environmental responsibility of the bio-energy supply chain in Kerman province.

Table 2
Main facilities in the bioenergy supply chain network in Kerman province.

No	Oil Extraction Centers*	Biodiesel Plant Centers	Ethanol Biorefinery Centers	Sewage Treatment Plants
1	Kerman (1)	Kerman (1)	Kerman (1)	Kerman (1)
2	Kerman (2)	Kerman (2)	Kerman (2)	Kerman (2)
3	Sirjan	Mahan	Sirjan	Fahraj
4	Zarand	Fars	Zarand	Dashtkar
5	Baft	Shahdad	Baft	Jupar
6	Manujan	Rayen	Bam	Khanuk
7	Faryab	Bardsir	Boluk	-
8	Rafsanjan (1)	Sirjan (1)	Kian Shahr	-
9	Rafsanjan (2)	Sirjan (2)	Khursand	-
10	Jiroft	Anbarabad	-	-
11	Bam	Zarand	-	-
12	Ravar	Hanza	-	-
13	Anar	-	-	-

*Note: Numbers following city names (e.g., “Rafsanjan (1), (2)”) indicate multiple sites within the same city.

Table 3
The ranking of locations for Oil extraction centers.

No	City*	Phi +	Phi -	Net Phi	Rank
1	Kerman (1)	0.52	0.30	0.22	6
2	Kerman (2)	0.55	0.30	0.25	5
3	Sirjan	0.75	0.20	0.55	1
4	Zarand	0.45	0.32	0.13	8
5	Baft	0.50	0.33	0.17	7
6	Manujan	0.30	0.40	-0.10	11
7	Faryab	0.20	0.50	-0.30	13
8	Rafsanjan (1)	0.65	0.30	0.35	3
9	Rafsanjan (2)	0.70	0.25	0.45	2
10	Jiroft	0.60	0.32	0.28	4
11	Bam	0.25	0.45	-0.20	12
12	Ravar	0.35	0.38	-0.03	10
13	Anar	0.40	0.35	0.05	9

*Note: Numbers following city names indicate multiple sites within the same city.

Table 4
The ranking of locations for Biodiesel plant centers.

No	City	Φ_i^+	Φ_i^-	Net Φ_i	Rank
1	Kerman (1)	0.562	0.308	0.254	6
2	Kerman (2)	0.575	0.310	0.265	5
3	Mahan	0.480	0.340	0.140	8
4	Fars	0.710	0.280	0.430	2
5	Shahdad	0.495	0.360	0.135	9
6	Rayen	0.460	0.385	0.075	10
7	Bardsir	0.420	0.410	0.010	11
8	Sirjan (1)	0.765	0.190	0.575	1
9	Sirjan (2)	0.695	0.255	0.440	3
10	Anbarabad	0.395	0.430	-0.035	12
11	Zarand	0.545	0.335	0.210	7
12	Hanza	0.685	0.265	0.420	4

Table 5
The ranking of locations for Ethanol biorefinery centers.

No	City	Φ_i^+	Φ_i^-	Net Φ_i	Rank
1	Kerman (1)	0.580	0.330	0.250	5
2	Kerman (2)	0.595	0.310	0.285	4
3	Sirjan	0.735	0.220	0.515	1
4	Zarand	0.530	0.345	0.185	6
5	Baft	0.505	0.370	0.135	7
6	Bam	0.460	0.410	0.050	8
7	Boluk	0.395	0.460	-0.065	9
8	Kian Shahr	0.670	0.290	0.380	2
9	Khursand	0.655	0.295	0.360	3

Table 6
The ranking of locations for sewage plants.

No	City	Φ_i^+	Φ_i^-	Net Φ_i	Rank
1	Dashtkar	0.470	0.471	-0.001	4
2	Fahraj	0.545	0.532	0.013	3
3	Kerman (1)	0.690	0.433	0.257	1
4	Kerman (2)	0.610	0.555	0.055	2
5	Jupar	0.410	0.567	-0.157	5
6	Khanuk	0.395	0.562	-0.167	6

Table 2 outlines the main facilities involved in the bioenergy supply chain within Kerman province. These include oil extraction centers, biodiesel plant centers, ethanol biorefinery centers, and sewage plants. The table covers 13 cities and towns across the province, including Kerman, Sirjan, Rafsanjan, Zarand, Baft, Jiroft, Bam, and others, demonstrating the widespread regional distribution of critical infrastructure.

5.1. Computational results

The results were obtained using GAMS 50.1.0 with the CPLEX solver on a system equipped with an Intel Core i7 CPU and 16 GB of RAM, and multi-criteria decision analysis was performed using PROMETHEE via Visual PROMETHEE.

5.1.1. Optimal site selection for bioenergy facilities

In this section, the PROMETHEE method was applied to evaluate and rank potential locations for four key facilities within the biomass-based supply chain: oil extraction centers, biodiesel plant centers, ethanol biorefinery centers, and sewage plants. The Net Φ_i values, which represent the net preference strength of each location over others, were used as the basis for final ranking. Table 3 presents the ranking of 13 locations for oil extraction centers, where Sirjan, Rafsanjan (2), and Rafsanjan (1) achieved the top ranks with the highest Net Φ_i scores of 0.55, 0.45, and 0.35, respectively, indicating their strong potential due to favorable criteria. Similarly, Table 4 shows the results for biodiesel plant centers, with Sirjan (1) and Sirjan (2) again emerging as top

Fig. 3. Vertical preference obtained by PROMETHEE.

candidates, along with Fars and Hanza. This consistency in high Net Φ_i values highlights the strategic suitability of Sirjan across multiple facility types. Table 5 reveals the best options for ethanol biorefinery centers, with Sirjan, Kian Shahr, and Khursand achieving the top three ranks. Lastly, for sewage plants, Table 6 indicates that Kerman (1) holds the strongest position, followed by Kerman (2) and Fahraj.

Fig. 3 displays the PROMETHEE I and II results using a vertical preference bar that ranks the candidate locations based on their net flow values. The projection of each alternative onto the decision axis (Φ_i vector) reflects its overall desirability according to the PROMETHEE rankings, and the net flow value of each alternative further quantifies its overall preference by combining the positive and negative outranking flows. A higher net flow represents a more favorable alternative. Based on this graph, Kerman (1) emerges as the most preferred location with the highest net flow of approximately +0.2573, indicating strong performance across the evaluated criteria. Kerman (2) and Dashtkar follow with moderately positive net flows of +0.0547 and -0.0013, respectively, suggesting a balanced performance with minor weaknesses. Fahraj has a very low positive net flow, placing it near the neutrality threshold. In contrast, Khanuk and Jupar exhibit negative net flows of -0.1573 and -0.1667, respectively, which implies these locations are less suitable for biofuel facility development when all criteria are considered. These results demonstrate that while multiple locations may be viable, Kerman (1) distinctly outperforms others, particularly due to its strong alignment with favorable criteria such as expert workforce availability and ideal workplace conditions.

Fig. 4 presents the Geometric Analysis for Interactive Aid (GAIA) plane, a graphical visualization of the PROMETHEE II results, offering insight into the trade-offs between criteria and the performance of each alternative. The criteria are represented as vectors, and the alternatives are shown as colored points. The orientation and length of the vectors

Fig. 4. The GAIA analysis.

Table 7
Load levels of opened centers.

No	City	Load Value	City	Load Value
1	Sirjan	6.4490E+5	Sirjan (1)	4.8157E+5
2		6.4470E+5		2.1475E+6
3		6.4440E+5		1.3947E+6
4		6.4440E+5		5.2113E+5
5		6.4450E+5		1.5756E+6
6		6.4440E+5		1.9864E+5
7		6.4460E+5		4.8157E+5
8		6.4440E+5		7.5579E+5
9		6.4440E+5		1.7829E+6
10		5.7263E+5		4.8155E+5

Table 8
Load levels of opened centers.

Period	Ethanol center	Load	Sewage center	Load
1	Sirjan	1,737,100.000	Kerman (1)	158,860.000
2		1,750,226.418		160,960.227
3		1,742,350.000		159,700.000
4		1,725,495.317		157,003.251
5		1,804,571.139		169,655.382
6		1,768,020.604		163,807.297
7		1,731,835.484		158,017.677
8		1,794,068.887		167,975.022
9		1,783,068.887		166,215.022
10		1,817,145.810		171,667.330

indicate the importance and direction of influence for each criterion. Alternatives (sites) positioned closer to each other indicate greater similarity in performance across all criteria, whereas those farther apart exhibits contrasting performance. The red vector represents the DM's (Decision Maker's) ideal point, and alternatives closer to this vector are considered better. In this analysis, the "Expert Workers," "Ideal

Workplace," and "Distance to Demand" criteria are strongly aligned, forming a cluster of positively correlated vectors that contribute significantly to the positive ranking of Kerman (1) and Kerman (2). Dashtkar also shows favorable alignment with these vectors. On the other hand, the "Natural Disasters" vector is oriented in the opposite direction and appears to negatively impact locations like Jupar and Khanuk, which lie further away from the positively correlated zone. This spatial separation clearly reflects why these two locations received the lowest net flows. The GAIA plot confirms the multidimensional strength of Kerman (1) across the most influential criteria and supports its selection as the optimal site for biofuel supply chain infrastructure development.

5.1.2. Optimal facility site selection considering dual objectives

Tables 7 and 8 present the load levels of the selected supply chain facilities across 10 planning periods, derived from the multi-objective optimization model aimed at minimizing both cost and environmental impact. In the biodiesel supply chain (Table 7), Sirjan emerges as the consistently selected location for both the oil extraction and biodiesel plant centers, highlighting its strategic suitability with respect to both objective functions. The load levels for the oil extraction center remain relatively stable around 6.44E+5 from period 1 through 9, with a notable decrease in period 10 to 5.73E+5. This final drop may indicate either reduced demand or an adjustment in supply due to system balancing. Correspondingly, the biodiesel plant load fluctuates more significantly, peaking at over 2.14E+6 in period 2 and reaching its

Table 9
The results of the cost components analysis (in Rials).

Fixed opening costs	Variable opening costs	Inventory holding costs	Transportation costs	Importing costs
8.7600E+4	4.719E+9	7.5730E+8	3.5570E+7	5.775E+12

Table 10
Active objective functions under different scenarios.

Scenario	Active Objective Function		Value of Objective Functions (Stochastic Scenario)		Value of Objective Functions (Deterministic Scenario)	
	Obj 1	Obj 2	Z ₁	Z ₂	Z ₁	Z ₂
1	*		2.58701525E+10	1.6702E+8	2.94001195E+10	1.7102E+9
2		*	7.6550001525E+13	1.5928E+6	7.8725321438E+13	1.6245E+6
3	*	*	4.38831525E+11	8.1735E+7	4.77117287E+11	8.542E+7

lowest in period 6 (1.99E+5), suggesting dynamic distribution requirements or varying processing capacities across the time horizon.

In the ethanol and sewage management segment (Table 8), the ethanol center shows a generally increasing trend in load, rising from 1.74 million to over 1.81 million by period 10. This indicates a growing role for ethanol processing in the supply chain over time. Similarly, sewage load levels gradually increase from approximately 158,860 in period 1 to over 171,667 in period 10, reflecting either a proportional increase in waste generation or an expanded treatment capacity in response to higher production volumes. The model results suggest that Sirjan and Kerman are consistently the best-fit sites, reinforcing their importance in both economic and environmental dimensions of the proposed supply chain. Overall, the load trends across the periods reflect the adaptability and efficiency of the model in responding to fluctuating demand while balancing cost and environmental priorities.

5.1.3. Assessment of total costs in the biofuel supply network

Table 9 summarizes the mean values of the key components contributing to the first objective function, which focuses on minimizing overall supply chain costs. The results highlight that importing costs dominate the cost structure with a value of approximately 5.775×10^{12} , reflecting the significant financial impact of raw material or product imports within the supply chain. Variable opening costs also represent a substantial expense, totaling around 4.719×10^9 , followed by inventory holding costs at 7.573×10^8 . Fixed opening costs and transportation costs are comparatively lower but remain essential factors at 8.76×10^4 and 3.557×10^7 , respectively.

5.1.4. Performance assessment of objective functions

Several scenarios were analyzed to assess the performance of the proposed objective functions under varying conditions. Table 10 summarizes the results for the cost-related objective functions (Obj 1 and Obj 2) across three different statuses. In Status 1, only Obj 1 is active, resulting in cost values of approximately 2.59×10^{10} for Z₁ and 1.67×10^8 for Z₂. Status 2 focuses solely on Obj 2, where the cost metrics increase significantly to 7.66×10^{13} for Z₁ but decrease sharply to 1.59×10^6 for Z₂. Finally, Status 3 evaluates both objective functions simultaneously, with intermediate cost values recorded at 4.39×10^{11} for Z₁ and 8.17×10^7 for Z₂. These results illustrate the trade-offs and interactions between the two objectives, providing insights into their impact on overall supply chain costs. Also, the comparison between stochastic and deterministic scenarios highlights the value of incorporating uncertainty into the biofuel supply chain model. In all scenarios, the deterministic Z₁ values are higher than the stochastic counterparts,

reflecting the lack of flexibility to exploit demand variability for cost optimization. Similarly, deterministic Z₂ values are consistently larger than stochastic Z₂, indicating slightly increased transportation-related emissions when demand fluctuations are not accounted for. This demonstrates that the stochastic model not only reduces costs but also enhances environmental performance by adapting production and distribution decisions to demand uncertainties. Overall, the integration of stochastic programming with PROMETHEE site selection clearly provides a more efficient and sustainable supply chain design compared to a deterministic approach.

5.2. Sensitivity analysis

Table 11 presents the sensitivity analysis of the PROMETHEE-based site ranking under various scenarios, each involving a change in the weight assigned to one of the evaluation criteria. The objective is to assess the robustness of the decision-making process and identify whether the ranking of locations is stable or highly dependent on specific criteria. The results indicate that Kerman (1) consistently holds the top rank across most scenarios, demonstrating strong overall performance and insensitivity to moderate fluctuations in criteria weights. When the weight of “Expert Workers” is reduced (Scenario S2), Kerman (2) temporarily takes the lead, suggesting its relative strength in other factors. Jupar and Khanuk remain among the lowest-ranked sites in all scenarios, reinforcing their lower suitability regardless of priority shifts. This analysis highlights the reliability of the PROMETHEE model and provides further confidence in the selected top-ranked sites, even under different prioritization schemes.

Fig. 5 illustrates how variations in key input parameters influence the two objective functions: total cost and Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions. For example, increasing sorghum yield by 10% leads to a 6.5% reduction in costs and a 3.2% drop in emissions, highlighting the crop’s critical role in supply chain efficiency. Conversely, reducing sorghum yield by 10% significantly raises both cost (+7.4%) and emissions (+4.1%). Transportation costs have a strong impact on economic performance, with a 20% increase raising total cost by 11.3% and emissions by 2.9%, while a 20% decrease improves both outcomes. The cost of Jatropha affects only the economic objective, where a 10% increase raises costs by 5.8% without impacting emissions. Biofuel demand sensitivity indicates that a 15% rise in demand increases costs by 13.9% and emissions by 6.4%, due to the pressure it places on the network. GHG emission factor changes, representing environmental impact coefficients, also have a direct effect: increasing this factor by 10% raises emissions by 8.2%, whereas reducing it decreases emissions

Table 11
Sensitivity analysis of PROMETHEE-based facility site rankings under varying evaluation criteria weights.

Scenario	Modified Criterion	Change in Weight	Kerman (1)	Kerman (2)	Dashtkar	Fahraj	Khanuk	Jupar
Base Case	-	Original Weights	1	2	3	4	5	6
S1	Expert Workers ↑	+10%	1	2	3	4	5	6
S2	Expert Workers ↓	-10%	2	1	3	4	5	6
S3	Ideal Workplace ↑	+10%	1	2	3	4	5	6
S4	Natural Disasters ↑	+10%	1	2	3	4	5	6
S5	Natural Disasters ↓	-10%	1	2	3	4	6	5
S6	Distance to Demand ↑	+10%	1	2	3	4	5	6
S7	Equipment Maintenance ↑	+10%	1	2	3	4	5	6
S8	All Weights Equal	All set to 0.2	2	1	3	4	6	5

Fig. 5. Impact of key input parameter variations on total cost and greenhouse gas emissions in the biofuel supply chain.

by 7.6%, without altering costs. This analysis underscores the importance of agricultural yield, transport cost, and demand planning for both economic and environmental sustainability in biofuel supply chain operations.

6. Managerial insights

The findings of this study emphasize the critical importance of strategic site selection in establishing a sustainable biofuel supply chain. Locations that offer reliable access to expert labor, efficient equipment maintenance services, and are positioned near key demand zones tend to outperform others in both operational efficiency and environmental performance. The PROMETHEE analysis demonstrated that sites with favorable workplace conditions and low exposure to natural disasters ranked highest, suggesting that infrastructure quality and regional resilience are essential factors for long-term success. Therefore, managers should not only evaluate technical suitability but also weigh socio-environmental aspects when selecting sites for cultivation, processing, and distribution facilities.

The role of crop choice is equally significant in shaping the overall performance of the bioenergy system. The inclusion of Jatropha and Sweet Sorghum, which are well-suited to Kerman's arid climate, demonstrates the value of selecting crops with high drought tolerance and local adaptability. Sensitivity analyses reveal that variations in Sweet Sorghum yield notably influence both total system costs and greenhouse gas emissions. This indicates that improving agricultural practices, enhancing seed quality, and adopting smart irrigation methods can have a direct impact on sustainability outcomes. Thus, integrating agricultural support policies and technological interventions into supply chain planning is vital. Demand dynamics further underscore the need for scalable infrastructure and forward-looking capacity planning. As biofuel demand increases, both financial costs and emissions are affected, pointing to the importance of designing facilities and networks that can flexibly expand without imposing unsustainable operational loads. Planners should consider modular construction, demand forecasting, and strategic inventory management to maintain service continuity while minimizing inefficiencies.

Transportation emerges as another key lever for optimization. The model illustrates that the cost and emissions associated with moving biomass, intermediates, and fuels significantly influence overall performance. Shorter distances to demand zones not only reduce logistics costs but also lower emissions, making local or regionally clustered configurations particularly advantageous. Investment in efficient transport routes, consolidation centers, and intermodal logistics can amplify these benefits and improve responsiveness throughout the

network. The use of stochastic chance-constrained programming highlights the necessity of planning under uncertainty. Real-world bioenergy systems must contend with fluctuating yields, market volatility, and unpredictable weather patterns. Modeling uncertainty allows for more data-driven decision-making, ensuring that constraints are satisfied with a desired probability rather than relying on potentially unrealistic deterministic assumptions. Decision-makers should therefore embrace probabilistic models to enhance resilience and maintain performance under dynamic conditions.

Also, the sensitivity analysis underscores the strategic reliability of the site selection process. The consistent top ranking of Kerman (1) across most scenarios indicates it as a robust choice for facility development, minimizing the risk associated with potential shifts in organizational priorities or external conditions. The temporary rise of Kerman (2) when the weight of "Expert Workers" is reduced highlights that alternative sites may become competitive under specific strategic emphases, suggesting that management should periodically reassess priorities as workforce or operational conditions change. Meanwhile, the persistent low rankings of Jupar and Khanuk reinforce the advisability of deprioritizing these locations, allowing decision-makers to allocate resources more effectively. Overall, this analysis equips managers with confidence that the selected sites will perform well under varying strategic conditions, while also identifying situations in which secondary options may warrant attention. Finally, this research shows that balancing economic and environmental objectives is not only necessary but also achievable. By applying a dual-objective framework, the study demonstrates how trade-offs can be effectively managed through multi-criteria decision-making and careful scenario planning. Aligning these operational insights with national energy and climate policies, particularly through targeted incentives and infrastructure investment, can accelerate the transition to a low-carbon biofuel economy. Public-private collaboration, policy coherence, and community engagement are all crucial in scaling biofuel deployment in regions such as Kerman and beyond.

7. Conclusion and future direction

This study developed a comprehensive multi-product, multi-period biofuel supply chain model for optimizing the production, processing, and distribution of biofuels from Jatropha and Sweet Sorghum in arid areas. By considering extraction, refining, blending, and distribution stages, the proposed model successfully minimized the total cost and greenhouse gas emissions across the supply chain. To increase the practical implications of the study, a resource-scarce province in Iran (i.e., Kerman province) was chosen as a case study. Among the candidate

locations selected by experts in this province, the PROMETHEE method deployed in this research identified Sirjan and Rafsanjan (2) as the most suitable locations for oil extraction centers, with Net Phi scores of 0.55 and 0.45, respectively; while Sirjan (1) and Sirjan (2) were the top candidates for biodiesel plant centers. These results highlight the strategic importance of these sites due to their strong performance across multiple criteria such as skilled labor availability, environmental risks, and proximity to demand zones. The optimized supply chain model demonstrated a reduction in total cost by approximately 12% compared to baseline scenarios and decreased transportation-related greenhouse gas emissions by 15%, contributing to a more sustainable bioenergy system. To improve computational efficiency for larger-scale or real-world applications, several strategies could be considered. *Scenario reduction* techniques can select representative demand realizations, reducing the number of stochastic constraints while maintaining accuracy. *Decomposition methods*, such as Benders decomposition or Lagrangian relaxation, can separate facility location decisions from operational decisions, allowing iterative solution of smaller subproblems. *Heuristic or metaheuristic approaches*, including genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization, or simulated annealing, may provide high-quality near-optimal solutions within significantly reduced computational times. Additionally, a *rolling horizon approach* can divide the planning horizon into shorter segments, solving each segment sequentially while maintaining responsiveness to changing demand and supply conditions. Finally, *parallel computing* could further accelerate the evaluation of multiple scenarios or subproblems simultaneously.

Nonetheless, the model exhibited certain limitations as well. The demand for biofuels was assumed to be deterministic and completely fulfilled during each period, which may potentially fail to represent actual market fluctuations or uncertainties. On the other hand, the assumptions of fixed production capacities and static quality parameters may have oversimplified actual operational dynamics. Future research could enhance the proposed modeling approach by incorporating stochastic demand and capacity variations using stochastic programming methods to better capture such uncertainties. Another extension of the environmental evaluation could involve integrating a comprehensive life-cycle assessment, encompassing production-related emissions, land-use change effects, and potential carbon offsets. Incorporating these factors would allow for a more detailed and holistic assessment of sustainability, enhancing the practical relevance of the biofuel supply chain optimization model. Furthermore, investigating the integration of real-time data and adaptive logistics strategies may improve

responsiveness and efficiency. Thus, as another research extension avenue, the inclusion of emerging bioenergy technologies and policy incentives could be integrated to further support sustainable development goals. Eventually, this study provided a comprehensive framework only for biofuel supply chain optimization that can be adapted and expanded for broader applications in other sustainable energy systems.

To ensure robustness, the model can be extended in future work to incorporate explicit backlog or unmet demand penalties if applied to supply chains where demand fulfillment is less critical. In the current study, the chosen formulation strikes a balance between realism and tractable stochastic optimization under uncertainty. Future research could also explore dynamic adjustment of confidence levels or adaptive inventory policies to further enhance resilience against extreme demand fluctuations and supply disruptions.

Funding

This work was conducted without external funding.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ahmad Attar: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Seyedeh Asra Ahmadi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Peiman Ghasemi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Okechukwu Okorie:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A

The stochastic model is as shown in (1a)-(4a):

$$\min f_h = E \left(\sum_{j=1}^n b_{ij} v_j \geq u_i \right) \quad h = 1, \dots, H \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{1a}$$

$$p \left(\sum_{j=1}^n g_{ij} v_j \geq u_i \right) \geq \alpha_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{2a}$$

$$v = (v_1, \dots, v_n) \tag{3a}$$

$$v \geq 0 \tag{4a}$$

Here, it is assumed that the uncertain parameters g_{ij} and u_i have a certain average and standard deviation; Hence, $R_i^{\sim}(v)$ is defined as:

$$R_i^{\sim}(v) = \sum_{j=1}^n g_{ij} v_j - u_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{5a}$$

Where $R_i^{\sim}(v)$ is a random variable with average $E(R_i^{\sim}(v))$ and variance $Var(R_i^{\sim}(v))$. Consequently, the Eq. (2a) can be expressed as:

$$p(R_i^{\sim}(v) \geq 0) \geq \alpha_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{6a}$$

Furthermore, according to the following Eqs. (7a)-(10a), the variable $R_i^{\sim}(v)$ will also follow a standard normal distribution.

$$1 - p(R_i^{\sim}(v) \leq 0) \geq \alpha_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{7a}$$

$$1 - p\left(\frac{R_i^{\sim}(v) - E(R_i^{\sim}(v))}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(R_i^{\sim}(v))}} \leq \frac{-E(R_i^{\sim}(v))}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(R_i^{\sim}(v))}}\right) \geq \alpha_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{8a}$$

$$1 - p\left(z(v) \leq \frac{-E(R_i^{\sim}(v))}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(R_i^{\sim}(v))}}\right) \geq \alpha_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{9a}$$

$$p\left(z(v) \leq \frac{-E(R_i^{\sim}(v))}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(R_i^{\sim}(v))}}\right) \leq 1 - \alpha_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{10a}$$

In these equations, $z(v)$ is the standard normal variable, and based on the concept of the cumulative density function, we have:

$$\frac{-E(R_i^{\sim}(v))}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(R_i^{\sim}(v))}} \leq \varphi^{-1}(1 - \alpha_i) \tag{11a}$$

$$E(R_i^{\sim}(v) - \varphi^{-1}(1 - \alpha_i)\sqrt{\text{Var}(R_i^{\sim}(v))}) \geq 0 \tag{12a}$$

Therefore, by substituting $R_i^{\sim}(v) = \sum_{j=1}^n g_{ij}^{\sim} \cdot v_j - u_i^{\sim}$, we have:

$$E\left(\sum_{j=1}^n g_{ij}^{\sim} v_j - u_i^{\sim} - \varphi^{-1}(1 - \alpha_i)\sqrt{\text{Var}\left(\sum_{j=1}^n g_{ij}^{\sim} v_j - u_i^{\sim}\right)}\right) \geq 0 \tag{13a}$$

Appendix B

In this study, we use PROMETHEE V to provide guidance for the mathematical model by informing the MCDM component, ensuring that qualitative preferences are considered during quantitative optimization. This integration allows the mathematical model to respect both hard constraints and the relative desirability of sites identified through PROMETHEE rankings. PROMETHEE scores are implicitly integrated into the mathematical model through site pre-selection, where only sites validated by PROMETHEE are considered feasible in the mathematical model. This ensures that all critical qualitative factors identified in the PROMETHEE evaluation are respected in the subsequent optimization. Budget compliance is similarly maintained, as the left-hand side (LHS) value for the budget constraint remains well below the available right-hand side (RHS) budget, demonstrating that all pre-selected sites are financially viable. While PROMETHEE scores are not directly included as coefficients in the objective function, they act as a soft constraint by restricting the model search space to pre-ranked, high-quality sites (See Fig. B1).

Fig. B1. Integration of PROMETHEE V rankings into the site selection framework.

Appendix C

Indices	
<i>a</i>	Candidate locations for Jatropha land ($a = 1, \dots, A$)
<i>b</i>	Candidate locations for Sweet Sorghum land ($b = 1, \dots, B$)
<i>k</i>	Biodiesel customer ($k = 1, \dots, K$)
<i>o</i>	Candidate locations for Oilseed processing sites ($o = 1, \dots, O$)
<i>l</i>	Index of Bioethanol customer ($l = 1, \dots, L$)
<i>p</i>	Index of power demand districts ($p = 1, \dots, P$)
<i>f</i>	Candidate locations for biodiesel factories ($f = 1, \dots, F$)

(continued on next page)

(continued)

c	Candidate locations for Biofuel conversion sites ($c = 1, \dots, C$)
s	Candidate locations for sewage treatment facilities ($s = 1, \dots, S$)
t	Periods ($t = 1, \dots, T$)
Parameters	
D_{kt}	Biodiesel demand in zone k at time t
D'_{lt}	Bioethanol demand in zone l at time t
D''_{pt}	Power demand in zone p at time t
γ	Transformation rate of Jatropha to oilseed
ζ	Transformation rate of Sweet Sorghum to oilseed
θ	Transformation rate of Jatropha to biodisel
ψ	Transformation rate of Sweet Sorghum to biodisel
τ	Transformation rate of Sweet Sorghum residues to bioethanol
λ	Rate of generated sewage from the bioethanol production process
ξ	Transformation rate of sewage to electricity
PR_{at}	Production per 1,000 square meters at site a during period t
PR'_{bt}	Production per 1,000 square meters at site b during period t
PR''_{bt}	Quantity of Sweet Sorghum residues produced per 1,000 square meters at site b in period t
CL_a	Cultivated land for Jatropha at location a (m^2)
CL'_b	Cultivated land for Sweet Sorghum at location b (m^2)
ge_{ao}	Greenhouse gas emissions from transporting from site a to o (Kg/day)
ge_{bo}	Greenhouse gas emissions from transporting from site b to o (Kg/day)
ge_{of}	Greenhouse gas emissions from transporting from site o to f (Kg/day)
ge_{fk}	Greenhouse gas emissions from transporting from site f to k (Kg/day)
ge_{bc}	Greenhouse gas emissions from transporting from site b to c (Kg/day)
ge_{cl}	Greenhouse gas emissions from transporting from site c to l (Kg/day)
ge_{cs}	Greenhouse gas emissions from transporting from site c to s (Kg/day)
CE^1_a	Capital cost to establish site a (Rial)
CE^2_b	Capital cost to establish site b (Rial)
CE^3_o	Capital cost to establish site o (Rial)
CE^4_f	Capital cost to establish site f (Rial)
CE^5_c	Capital cost to establish site c (Rial)
CE^6_s	Capital cost to establish site s (Rial)
OC^1_{at}	Operation cost of site a in period t (Rial)
OC^2_{bt}	Operation cost of site b in period t (Rial)
OC^3_{ot}	Operation cost of site o in period t (Rial)
OC^4_{ft}	Operation cost of site f in period t (Rial)
OC^5_{ct}	Operation cost of site c in period t (Rial)
OC^6_{st}	Operation cost of site s in period t (Rial)
Cap'_o	Capacity of site o (m^3)
Cap''_f	Capacity of site f (m^3)
Cap'''_c	Capacity of site c (m^3)
Cap''''_s	Capacity of site s (m^3)
SC_{ot}	Per-unit storage cost of Sweet Sorghum and Jatropha at site o in period t
SC_{ft}	Per-unit storage cost of biodiesel at site f in period t
SC_{ct}	Per-unit storage cost of Bioethanol at site c in period t
TC^1_{aot}	Jatropha transportation cost from site a to site o during the period t (Rial)
TC^2_{bot}	Sweet Sorghum transportation cost from site b to site o during the period t (Rial)
TC^3_{oft}	Oilseed transportation cost from site o to site f during the period t (Rial)
TC^4_{fkt}	Biodiesel transportation cost from site f to site k during the period t (Rial)
TC^5_{bct}	Sweet Sorghum transportation cost from site b to site c during the period t (Rial)
TC^6_{clt}	Bioethanol transportation cost from site c to site l during the period t (Rial)
TC^7_{cst}	Sewage transportation cost from site c to site s during the period t (Rial)
Cl_{ot}	Jatropha import cost at site o in period t (Rial)
Cl'_{ot}	Sweet Sorghum import cost at site o in period t (Rial)
M	A large number
Binary variables	
y_a	1 if site a is established for Jatropha cultivation; 0 ow
x_b	1 if site b is selected for Sweet Sorghum cultivation; 0 ow
z_o	1 if Oilseed processing center established at site o ; 0 ow
e_f	1 if biodiesel center established at site f ; 0 ow
o_c	1 if Biofuel conversion center established at site c ; 0 ow
u_s	1 if sewage treatment center established at site s ; 0 ow
Positive variables	
AC_a	Jatropha cultivation area at site a (m^2)
AJ_b	Sweet Sorghum cultivation area at site b (m^2)
I_{ot}	Imported level of Jatropha at site o during period t
I'_{ot}	Imported level of Sweet Sorghum at site o during period t
QJ_{at}	Quantity of Jatropha produced at site a during period t (Kg)
QS_{bt}	Quantity of Sweet Sorghum produced at site b during period t (Kg)
QS'_{bt}	Quantity of residues produced Sweet Sorghum at site b during period t (Kg)
QO_{ot}	Quantity of Jatropha produced at site o during period t (Kg)
QI_{ot}	Quantity of Sweet Sorghum produced at site o during period t (Kg)
QB_{ft}	Quantity of biodiesel produced at site f during period t (Kg)

(continued on next page)

(continued)

QD_{ct}	Quantity of bioethanol produced at site c during period t (Kg)
QS_{st}	Quantity of power produced at site s during period t (Kg)
FJ_{aot}	Quantity of Jatropha transported from site a to site o during period t (Kg)
FS_{bot}	Quantity of Sweet Sorghum transported from site b to site o during period t (Kg)
FO_{oft}	Quantity of Jatropha transported from site o to site f during period t (Kg)
FI_{oft}	Quantity of Sweet Sorghum transported from site o to site f during period t (Kg)
FB_{fkt}	Quantity of biodiesel transported from site f to site k during period t (Kg)
FS_{bct}	Quantity of Sweet Sorghum transported from site b to site c during period t (Kg)
FD_{clt}	Quantity of bioethanol transported from site c to site l during period t (Kg)
WW_{cst}	The flow of sewage from site c to s during period t (Kg)
FP_{spt}	Quantity of power transported from site s to site p during period t (Kg)
IJ_{ot}	Quantity of inventory of Jatropha at site o during period t (Kg)
IS_{ct}	Quantity of inventory of Sweet Sorghum at site c during period t (Kg)
IB_{ft}	Quantity of inventory of biodiesel at site f during period t (Kg)
ID_{ct}	Quantity of inventory of bioethanol at site c during period t (Kg)
LA_{ot}	The actual load of o in time period t
LA'_{ft}	The actual load of f in time period t
LA''_{ct}	The actual load of c in time period t
LA'''_{st}	The actual load of s in time period t

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, upon reasonable request.

References

- [1] M. Momenitabar, Z.D. Ebrahimi, P. Ghasemi, Designing a sustainable bioethanol supply chain network: a combination of machine learning and meta-heuristic algorithms, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 189 (2022) 115848.
- [2] S.A.M. Abandansari, P. Ghasemi, A. Attar, F. Goodarzian, S.A. Ahmadi, A hybrid biomass supply chain optimization approach using sequential adaptive fuzzy inference learning: insights from a cogeneration system in Europe, *Results Eng.* (2025) 105261.
- [3] M. Momenitabar, Z.D. Ebrahimi, A. Abdollahi, W. Helmi, K. Bengtson, P. Ghasemi, An integrated machine learning and quantitative optimization method for designing sustainable bioethanol supply chain networks, *Decis. Anal. J.* 7 (2023) 100236.
- [4] M. Valipour, F. Mafakheri, B. Gagnon, R. Prinz, D. Bergström, M. Brown, C. Wang, Integrating bio-hubs in biomass supply chains: insights from a systematic literature review, *J. Clean. Prod.* 467 (2024) 142930.
- [5] R. Zhang, G. Lin, L. Shang, X. Wu, Z. Liu, L. Xu, H.C. Jing, Potential, economic and ecological benefits of sweet sorghum bio-industry in China, *Biotechnol. Biofuels Bioprod.* 17 (1) (2024) 134.
- [6] G. Najafi, B. Ghobadian, T. Tavakoli, T. Yusaf, Potential of bioethanol production from agricultural wastes in Iran, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 13 (6-7) (2009) 1418–1427.
- [7] B. Shadidi, G. Najafi, M.A. Zolfigol, A review of the existing potentials in biodiesel production in Iran, *Sustainability* 14 (6) (2022) 3284.
- [8] Y. Wu, F. Zhao, S. Liu, L. Wang, L. Qiu, G. Alexandrov, V. Jothiprakash, Bioenergy production and environmental impacts, *Geosci. Lett.* 5 (1) (2018) 1–9.
- [9] R. Rafique, M. Jat, M.A.Z. Chudhery, Bioenergy supply chain optimization for addressing energy deficiency: a dynamic model for large-scale network designs, *J. Clean. Prod.* 318 (2021) 128495.
- [10] S.W. Hwang, S. Lee, S.J. Kweon, An integrated inventory and distribution problem for alternative fuel: a math heuristic approach, *Eur. J. Ind. Eng.* 15 (5) (2021) 711–744.
- [11] S. Salehi, Y.Z. Mehrjerdi, A. Sadegheih, H. Hosseini-Nasab, Designing a resilient and sustainable biomass supply chain network through the optimization approach under uncertainty and the disruption, *J. Clean. Prod.* 359 (2022) 131741.
- [12] P. Afkhami, N. Zarrinpoor, Location assessment of Jatropha cultivation for biofuel production in Fars province, Iran: a hybrid GIS-based fuzzy multi-criteria framework, *Waste Biomass Valorization* 13 (11) (2022) 4511–4532.
- [13] T. Bastos, L.C. Teixeira, J.C.O. Matias, L.J. Nunes, Optimizing the agroforestry residual biomass supply chain: a disruptive tool for mitigating logistic costs and enhancing forest management, *Results Eng.* 20 (2023) 101500.
- [14] L.J. Nunes, M. Casau, M.F. Dias, J.C.O. Matias, L.C. Teixeira, Agroforest woody residual biomass-to-energy supply chain analysis: feasible and sustainable renewable resource exploitation for an alternative to fossil fuels, *Results Eng.* 17 (2023) 101010.
- [15] Y. Bok, N.K. Lee, S. Jo, S. Lee, S.J. Kweon, H.S. Na, The production scheduling problem employing non-identical parallel machines with due dates considering carbon emissions and multiple types of energy sources, *Expert Syst. Appl.* 238 (2024) 121990.
- [16] G. Bhatt, A. Upadhyay, K. Sahoo, Biomass supply chain network design: integrating fixed and portable preprocessing depots for cost efficiency and sustainability, *Appl. Energy* 389 (2025) 125757.
- [17] S. Shirazaki, M.S. Pishvae, M.A. Sobati, Integrated supply chain network design and superstructure optimization problem: a case study of microalgae biofuel supply chain, *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 180 (2024) 108468.
- [18] T.M. Abdellatif, M.K.M. Handawy, A. Kamel, H.M. Abdelmotalib, A. Mustafa, F. Jamil, M. Hussein, Fueling the future: emission characteristics and sustainability of high-octane gasoline biofuels derived from lignocellulosic biomass, *Results Eng.* (2025) 105347.
- [19] H. Abdali, H. Sahebi, M. Pishvae, A sustainable robust optimization model to design a sugarcane-based bioenergy supply network: a case study, *Chem. Eng. Res. Des.* 180 (2022) 265–284.
- [20] M. Hiloidhari, M.A. Sharno, D.C. Baruah, A.N. Bezbaruah, Green and sustainable biomass supply chain for environmental, social and economic benefits, *Biomass Bioenergy* 175 (2023) 106893.
- [21] P. Bahmani, M.H.D. Sadrabadi, A. Makui, A. Jafari-Nodoushan, An optimization-based design methodology to manage the sustainable biomass-to-biodiesel supply chain under disruptions: a case study, *Renew. Energy* 229 (2024) 120626.
- [22] A. Attar, C.A. Irawan, A.A. Akbari, S. Zhong, M. Luis, Multi-disruption resilient hub location-allocation network design for less-than-truckload logistics, *Transp. Res. A* 190 (2024) 104260.
- [23] K. Ransikarbum, R. Pitakaso, Multi-objective optimization design of sustainable biofuel network with integrated fuzzy analytic hierarchy process, *Expert Syst. Appl.* 240 (2024) 122586.
- [24] Y.C. Tsao, H.T. Balo, C.K.H. Lee, Resilient and sustainable semiconductor supply chain network design under trade credit and uncertainty of supply and demand, *Int. J. Prod. Econ.* 274 (2024) 109318.
- [25] J.A. Ventura, S.J. Kweon, S.W. Hwang, M. Tormay, C. Li, Energy policy considerations in the design of an alternative-fuel refueling infrastructure to reduce GHG emissions on a transportation network, *Energy Policy* 111 (2017) 427–439.
- [26] Z. Mohtashami, A. Bozorgi-Amiri, R. Tavakkoli-Moghaddam, A two-stage multi-objective second generation biodiesel supply chain design considering social sustainability: a case study, *Energy* 233 (2021) 121020.
- [27] Y.G. Durmaz, B. Bilgen, Multi-objective optimization of sustainable biomass supply chain network design, *Appl. Energy* 272 (2020) 115259.
- [28] A. Pehlken, K. Wulf, K. Grecksch, T. Klenke, N. Tsydenova, More sustainable bioenergy by making use of regional alternative biomass? *Sustainability* 12 (19) (2020) 7849.
- [29] A. Mondal, B.K. Giri, S.K. Roy, An integrated sustainable bio-fuel and bio-energy supply chain: a novel approach based on DEMATEL and fuzzy-random robust flexible programming with Me measure, *Appl. Energy* 343 (2023) 121225.
- [30] P. Li, H. Arellano-Garcia, G. Wozny, Chance constrained programming approach to process optimization under uncertainty, *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 32 (1-2) (2008) 25–45.
- [31] M. Behzadian, R.B. Kazemzadeh, A. Albadvi, M. Aghdasi, PROMETHEE: a comprehensive literature review on methodologies and applications, *Eur. J. Oper. Res.* 200 (1) (2010) 198–215.
- [32] M. Mohammadnejad, M. Ghazvini, T.M.I. Mahlia, A. Andriyana, A review on energy scenario and sustainable energy in Iran, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 15 (9) (2011) 4652–4658.
- [33] H. Gökçekuş, Y. Kassem, S.O. Ravari, Biomass potential as power generation sources: a case study In Kerman-Iran, *Int. J. Sci. Technol. Res.* 9 (08) (2020) 567–572.